

DEMOGRAPHIC DIVIDENDS AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: A SOCIOLOGICAL PARLANCE

Udom Sunday Daniel¹
Victor E. Ben²

¹Department of Sociology and Anthropology
Akwa Ibom State University
Obio Akpa Campus
udomdaniel@aksu.edu.ng

²Department of Sociology and Anthropology
University of Uyo, Uyo
victorben@uniuyo.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study examined demographic dividends and socio-economic developments in Nigeria. The study reveals the relationship between demographic dividends, human capital development, and the socio-economic development of Nigeria. The study employs Thomas Malthus's theory of population growth. This study adopted the documentary/content method of data collection and content analysis in the discussion of findings. The essence of adopting this approach of data collection was to help us assess a set of documents for the creation of a larger narrative through the study of multiple documents that focused on the study of demographic dividends and socio-economic developments in Nigeria to bring about sociological parlance. In the analysis, the study identifies social inequality as one of the pitfalls hindering the achievement of demographic dividends in Nigeria. The study also reveals ill health, poverty, illiteracy, and large family size as factors that influence the growth rate of demographic variables, and the achievement of socioeconomic development in the country. It is noted that family size or population structure correlates with the provisions of health care services, literacy rate, good governance and economic development, thus enhancing demographic dividends in Nigeria. It concludes that attending demographic dividend in a country is dependent on the population structure, and for it to be achieved, excessive population growth should be checked.

Keywords: Demographic dividends, socio-economic development, and Sociological parlance.

INTRODUCTION

Studies by USAID (2022), revealed that African Countries have experienced sustained economic growth which has manifested in increased productivity, income

generation and cash flow. But despite this growth, almost two of every three people are living on less than two dollars (\$2) per day. However, to reduce this imbalance of inequality and poverty USAID noted that improving people's lives across Africa depends on accelerated economic growth which will enhance an economic window of opportunity based on a rapid decline in fertility, which increased the proportion of working-age people relative to dependent children. In this Ben (2024) and Daniel, Udousoro and Effiong (2024) submit that could be achieved government's response to improved health care and education standards, attracting foreign investments and enacting economic policies will address the challenge and create jobs for the people. Therefore when a country gets to this level, it is considered to have attended the point of demographic dividend (Gribble and Bremner, 2012b).

The demographic dividend has become an integral part of many development policy strategies, and the phenomenon has become very critical due primarily to the increasing demands and expectations of the citizenry particularly in third-world countries and the responsibilities of the government to its people (Daniel, Udousoro, and Effiong, 2024). Demographic dividends describe a boost to economic growth for societies at the beginning of their demographic transition. Interestingly, as employment challenges become heightened and poverty irreducible, much of the public demands in third-world countries are financed from public resources. A study of these indicates a country's characteristics that are bedevilled with a high rate of population growth, unemployment; poor social services provisions and other pressures associated with a lowering mortality rate, an upward trend in fertility as well as a high and unabated migration (Daniel and Ben, 2024).

Demographic dividends refer to the growth in an economy, which has to do with a change in the age structure of a country's population, caused by a decline in the fertility and mortality rates. According to Kenton (2020), a country that experiences a low birth rate in conjunction with low death rates receives an economic dividend and benefits from the increase in productivity of the working population that ensues. That is as fewer births are registered; the number of young dependents grows smaller relative to the working population of the society. To Kenton, where there are fewer people to support and more people in the labour force, the economy's resources are freed up and invested in other areas to celebrate a country's economic development and the future prosperity of its populace.

Gribble and Bremner (2012), for a country to achieve a demographic dividend, it must go through a transition in its demographic structure which moves from a largely rural agrarian economy with high fertility and mortality rates to an urban industrial society characterized by low fertility and mortality rates. The transformation of the rural economy according to Mboho, Udom, and Ekoriko (2024) will equally make this possible as it will help to reduce rural-urban migration. The challenge of Nigeria's demographic dividend has been invaded by a high population growth experience which has been on a positive/ratio increase in the last four decades. Thus weakening the viability of migration, increased fertility, morbidity and mortality will boost the productive age of Nigeria and save the country from dependency and the arrow of demographic setback.

A demographic dividend is a concept used in explaining the accelerated economic growth that accrues to a nation as a result of the decline in mortality and fertility rate of the nation facilitated by a change in the age structure of the population of such a country. Observably, lower mortality and fertility manifest in an increased working age ratio of the total population, and a decrease in dependency age. In Nigeria, this is different as what we

experience is a growing population with a fertility rate of 5.1%, a growth rate of 2.39% and 5.0% unemployment as well as an inflation level/rate of in the third quarter of 2023 leading to inequality and an unachievable dividend from the demographic structure.

Arising from the above, Nigeria experiences a population increase of 48,383,961.00 between 2015-2024 (229,521,409 and 181,137,448.00) making it unattainable for the dividends of demography. And sandwiched by unchecked population growth with a corresponding level of social inequality and unemployment, it could therefore be said that the socioeconomic development of Nigeria has been flawed by the variables of demography.

On the strength of the above and manifested by the experience of inequality in social provisions like education, health, housing, employment and income level about age distribution and quality of the population, this study, hopes to examine why the country has not been able to make the most dividends out of its expanding working age population, as well explain the inevitability of social inequality as well as identify the factors responsible for the social imbalance.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Principally, the study hoped to assess the pitfalls of demographic dividends in the achievement of socioeconomic development in Nigeria.

Specifically; the study shall;

1. Identify the causes of social inequality and its effects in achieving demographic dividends in the country.
2. Create a link between the growth rate of demographic variables and the socio-economic development of the country.
3. Suggest ways of balancing the demographic characteristics with the socio-economic development of the country.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept and Overview of Demographic Dividend

Demographic dividend is a process of economic growth that accrues to a country or state as a result of the decline in mortality and fertility rate subsequent upon the change in the age structure of the population (Bloom, Canning and Sevillan, 2003). It is an accelerated economic growth that a country experiences in response to its effort to control the excesses of population growth. Daniel, Udousoro and Effiong (2024) noted that a country will achieve its balance when a lower mortality and fertility rate leads to an increase in the working age, reduces the level of dependency and increases a nation's socio-economic development.

Bloom, Canning and Sevilla (2003) in a study of demographic dividend submitted that lower mortality and fertility levels reduce the dependency ratio of the total population and the outcome of such an effect will be a strong, positive effect on economic growth, and an accompanied appropriate socio-economic development. World Bank (2015), noted that though the potential of demographic dividend in a given country or state is attainable, its realization and the magnitude of such realizations are never automatic. As such manifestation would depend on their current demographic profile and the trends in their demographic changes as well as their ability to create an appropriate enabling environment for development.

From the above, enabling environment, according to Willie, Mboho and Udom

(2023); Saviour Udom and Clement (2024) involves the improvements in governance and government machinery including the economy, healthcare services (family planning), education, employment opportunities (job creation) and income generation. Deducing from the above, an increase in demographic dividends could be attained not only through the increase in the working age ratio but the creation of an enabling environment for investment and development; that is where the environment is made conducive for investment, potential investors will be attracted to the area and both human and social capital will be developed.

According to Canning, Rraja and Yazbeck (2015), rights are not equally distributed same as privileges and opportunities as well as status for all citizens in human societies. But the fact remains that in some the disparity is saddled by the population differentials and the gap is wider than what is obtained in others. The study opined that lower adolescent fertility creates a positive circle of benefits by improving the life chances of the citizens by creating an equilibrium point where the population and the dividends meet. This helps to ensure that citizens have better life chances; via attainment in education, health services, housing, skills acquisition, other social benefits etc and the nation's overall development. This is the situation in third world countries and Nigeria in particular where 5.3% of the population are unemployed and a property level of 38.8%. With different professing strategies, the ratio of attaining dividends remains high as a result of the unstable characteristics of demographics in the country (Daniel, Udousoro, and Effiong 2024).

The Concept of Demographic Dividend

The concept of demographic dividend has become an integral part of many development policy strategies. The term describes a boost to economic growth for countries at the beginning of their demographic transition, and as noted earlier, the actualization as well as the level of such dividend is not automatic but rather depends on the country's current demographic profile and the trends in their demographic changes.

However, as a concept, demographic dividend implies the relationship that exists between a country's demographic profile and its potential for an increase in economic growth (Statistics, South Africa 2017). It is an accelerated economic growth that accrues to a country or state, as a result of decline in mortality and fertility rate and subsequent change in the age structure of the population. The analysis has it that in a situation where a country's mortality and fertility rates begins to decline, population growth will be slow. The implication of the above is that the youth dependency ratio will fall and the working age population rises thus leading to a boost in the growth of per capital income, savings and investments (Ahmed and Cruz, 2016).

Demographic dividend, as defined by the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA, 2015) is an economic growth potential that can result from a shifts in a population's age structure, mainly when the state of the working, age population (18-65) is larger than the non-working age share of the population (14 and younger, and 66 and older). In Sum, demographic dividend is a boost in economic productivity that occurs when members of the work force is high in relative to the members of dependent class UNFPA (2015) noted that a nation with both increasing members of young people and declining fertility has the potential to reap a demographic dividends.

Population Growth, Social Inequality and Demographic Dividend

Population growth, social inequality and demographic dividend are interdependent concepts. Nigeria's population is a rapidly growing one estimated to reach about 400 million in 2050, with a high proportion of youths (Daniel, Udousoro, Effiong 2024); 70% of the population been less than 30 years and less than 15 years at 42%. Nigeria has struggle against demographic tide with a widening gaps in poverty, unemployment, and inequality which are factors influencing the countries underdevelopment.

Studies by Ochinabo, (2021), posits that the population of Nigeria in the last ten years (2014-2024) has significantly created an unequal gap in the human development index of the country, that data (see table on Nigeria's Population Growth, and Unemployment Rate) in the first quarter of 2024 shows an unemployment level of 5.3% against 5.0% in 3rd quarter in 2023 with a corresponding poverty level of 38.8% in 2024. Ochinaho (2021), however, identified population growth as the bane to achieving social equality and an enhanced demographic dividend in Nigeria. It further noted that for the country to attend the level of demographic dividend, it must be able to control its rapidly growing population and also institute policies that will attract investors to the country. The author also noted that inclusive economic policies when properly instituted will reduce youth unemployment by developing skills set through quality education, improved healthcare and vocational training for the actualization of demographic dividend in the country.

The UN (2023) reports show that more than half of the Nigerian Population still grapples with extreme poverty. The report provides a picture of the current state of poverty and economic inequality in the country, identifies the main drivers of this situation and presents some policy solutions. The share of Nigerians living below that poverty line indicates 43.3% in 2014 to 40.7% in 2024, equivalent to 93,264,952 of the population.

Nigeria's Population Growth and Unemployment Rate Data 2014-2024

Year	Population Growth Rate	Growth Rate (%)	Unemployment rate (%)
2024	229,152,217	2.39	4.52
2023	223,804,632	2.41	3.07
2022	218,541,212	2.41	3.83
2021	213,401,323	2.44	5.39
2020	208,327,405	2.47	5.71
2019	203,304,492	2.48	5.21
2018	198,387,623	2.53	5.07
2017	193,495,907	2.56	4.89
2016	188,666,931	2.54	4.52
2015	183,995,783	2.57	4.11
2014	179,379,016	2.66	3.88

Source: United Nations-World Population Prospects

Implementing Strategic Needed Areas for The Realization of Demographic Dividends in Nigeria

For countries like Nigeria to realize their demographic dividend, they must make strategic investments in four key areas as follows;

(i) **Initiating Demographic Change:** The first step towards attending a demographic dividend by a country is by ensuring a rapid fertility decline through investment in family planning, child survival and educating the girl's child. This will lead to a shift in a population's age structure thus enhancing a much more working age than the dependent – non-working age.

According to Udom and Tahirih (2024), when adolescent fertility is lowered, it will create a positive circle of benefits by improving the chances of adolescent girls and also help to ensure their educational development, as well as contributing to the nation's economic development and individuals skills acquisition that can help them find better jobs. Without increased investments in family planning, Udom and Tahirih (2024); Udom and Victor (2024) noted that Nigeria may miss her opportunity for a demographic dividend. However, to achieve the level of demographic dividend, the authors documented that Nigeria needs an increase in investments and political will to support family planning programmes to reduce population growth.

In sum, it could therefore be noted that lowering fertility levels and shifting the age structure of the population in marriage and childbirth is the first stage in achieving a demographic dividend.

(ii) Improving People's Health: Healthy Children do better in school, and this success ultimately contributes to a higher-skilled labour force. To achieve economic productivity health services to workers are therefore important and maintaining their health needs is therefore critical to national growth.

(iii) Investment in Education: The education system according to USAIDS (2013) should focus on ensuring that more young people acquire the needed training and skills needed to adapt to the changing socio-economic environment. Importantly, when education is prioritized, it open and access for both boys and girls to attend formal education and where this is the case, it makes accelerated economic growth possible. Education according Udom and Victor (2024) helps to delay marriage and first pregnancy, making family size therefore few, by having delayed or postponed early marriage for education. Thus the study encourages education for all, health care services and awareness that will help prevent population explosion in Nigeria if her demographic dividend is to be achieved.

It is worth noting that, as countries move through the demographic dividend process, they will need to adapt appropriate educational policies that will boost their changing economic situation and enhance national development.

(iv) Implementing Economic and Governance Policies: It is important to note that achieving demographic dividend should be anchored on government implementing policies that will boast good governance and such economic policies that will foster job creation and investment in labour intensive sectors, support the expansion of infrastructure base of the nation and promote trade to ensure access to international market as well as create a secure environment and incentive for development. According to USAID (2013) demographic dividends is then achieved when the population structure of the country is said to be healthy, educated, investment driven through government policies targeted for the state economic development.

From the above point of view, the key point underlying the demographic dividend is that population age structure – dependency ratio – is critically important and even more so than the population size. People are at the heart of the demographic dividend, and the extent to which countries reap these dividends varies and depends on the policies adopted in health, education, economy by the government.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Thomas Malthus theory (1766-1834) of population growth is adopted for this study. The English scholar Reverend Thomas Malthus published a population theory titled; 'An Essay on the Principle of Population'. According to the theory, Malthus noted that over population was the cause of many of the social ills affecting the attainment of demographic dividends and socio-economic development of a society.

The theory has it that where the population out space their local carrying capacity causing the inability of the ecosystems to support resource growth; attainment of demographic dividends will be in shamble. Demographic dividend as well as the socio-economic development of any particular society like Nigeria when measured by this theory can only be enhanced when the population is under checked and not allowed to exceed resource growth and capacity.

In accordance to Thomas Malthus over population growth is the cause of poverty, famine, environmental degradation and in addition large family size, illiteracy, ill health, and inequality that inevitably impede the attainment of demographic dividends. However, it is in line to state that demographic dividend and socio-economic development of Nigeria is significantly dependent on the rate of growth and viability of its population. That is, where the family size is large, it is expedient that it will affects the variables of demographic dividends as witness in labour supply, healthcare, savings, human capital and economic growth of the nation.

In line with Malthus submission, it is therefore pertinent to infer that where a population structure is not allowed to exceed its carrying capacity, health services will be enhanced, education accessed by all, good governance, economic growth achievable and demographic dividends possible,

From the above point of view, it is imperative to note that achieving demographic dividends in Nigeria is affected by the high population growth rate of 2.39% which manifested in 4.52% of unemployment rate. To overcome these it should deduced that key points underlying the attainment of demographic dividends be moderated to reflect the goals of sustainable development. This theory, therefore, concludes that achieving demographic dividends demands a critical pursuit of the variables of demography via; healthcare, educational attainment, social equality, economic development and importantly the management of population age structure, avoiding dependency and enhancement of self-reliance thus availing demographic dividends for the people.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the documentary/content method of data collection and content analysis in the discussion of findings. A documentary method is an approach to data collection that uses secondary and official documents as source material for data collection. The documents include information generated from newspapers, diaries, directories and already published works. The essence of adopting this approach of data collection was to help us assess a set of documents for the creation of a larger narrative through the study of multiple documents that focused on the study of demographic dividends and socio-economic developments in Nigeria to bring about sociological parlance.

SUMMARY/RECOMMENDATIONS

A demographic dividend occurs when the proportion of the working population in a total population is higher than the dependent population, (Akwa Ibom State, 2018), and this indicate that more people have the potential to be productive and to contribute to the growth of the economy. Daniel, Udousoro and Effiong (2024) postulate that for economic growth to occur, the younger population must have access to quality education, adequate nutrition and health care including access to sexual and reproductive health. However, it is important to

note that the fewer the younger dependents as a result of declining fertility and child mortality rates, as well as fewer older dependents, with the largest segment of the population at their productive working age, the lower the dependency ratio thus leading to demographic dividends. The study employs Thomas Malthus's Population theory. Qualitative in nature, the study adopted a documentary/content method of data collection and a thematic approach in the discussion of data.

From the above standpoint, a combination of effective public policies will help to facilitate more rapid economic growth, improve livelihood and put less strain on families, enhancing women's education and in the labour force as well as raising income and life expectancies. It is important to note that such a shift typically leads to an increase in the working population's productivity, boosting per capita income.

The need for demographic dividend by a country influences its investment in education and healthcare, as it is believed that such investment will significantly reduce fertility rates and infant mortality. Importantly, where the education of the citizens is prioritized especially that of the girl child, it will break the negative barriers and perception of family planning, reducing the societal norms for family size, while increasing the average life expectancy as well as the portion of the population that is in the working age-group, and reduces spending on dependents and spurs economic growth – thus we have more hands that earns and less mouths to feed. It could be noted therefore that where a country attends demographic dividend, it will have more people who have the potentials for economic gains thus enhancing their productive level and contributions to the growth of the nations socio-economic.

Also, since attending demographic dividends will require rural community transformation. Demographic dividend is therefore relevance in that its attainment helps to transform the rural agrarian economy with high fertility rates to an urban industrialized economy with low fertility and mortality rates. Rural cooperation, job creation and self-reliance. Where the above is realized, demographic dividend will increase savings, expand the workforce, increase human capital, and drive growth.

Significantly, demographic dividend attracts foreign investment since there is a ready man power or labour force for engagement in any established organization, promote the export of locally manufactured goods, and create a minimum wage to raise standards of living-this will laid a foundation for socio-economic development. This strategy also extend health, education and economic opportunities for the reach of the rural poor, reducing rural-urban migration and extending/opening up new cities in the rural areas as well as establishment of microfinance/small co-operative societies with low-interest loans for economic opportunities/support to improve the rural economic setting.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, S. A., Cruz, M., Quillin, B. and Schellekens, P. (2016). Demographic change and Development: *Looking at Challenges and Opportunities Through a New Typology*. Policy Research Working Paper 7893. Development Prospect Group, World Bank.
- Ahmed, S. A. and Cruz, M. (2016). *Making the most of Demographic change in Southern Africa*. Background Paper. Development Prospects Group, World Bank.
- Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development, Labour and Manpower Planning (2018). *Akwa Ibom Demographic Dividend Profile*. Uyo: Akwa Ibom State Ministry

- of Economic Development, Labour and Manpower Planning.
- Bloom, D. E., Canning, D. and Sevilla, J. (2003). *The Demographic Dividend: A New Perspective on the Economic Consequences of Population Change*. Santa Monica CA: RAND.
- Canning, D., Rraja, S. and Yazbeck, A. S., Editors (2015). *Africa's Demographic Transition: Dividend or Disaster? Africa Development Forum*; Washington, DC: World Bank; and Agence Francaise de Development.
- Daniel, U. S., Udousoro, T. E. and Effiong, U. U. (2024). Population Drift, Crime Rate and Socio-Economic Development in Uyo Capital City of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *AKSU Annals of Sustainable Development*, vol. 2(1): 2024. ISSN (P):3027-0499; ISSN: (E) 3043-4955 <https://doi.org/10.60787/AASD-v2i1-36>
- Daniel, U. S. and Udousoro, T. E. (2024). Determinants of Preference of Abortion and Non-Utilisation of Family Planning Services among Women of Child Bearing Age in Rural Communities of Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, Volume 2, Issues 2, April, 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11103575.
- Daniel, U. S. and Ben, V. E. (2024). Fertility Behaviour and Family Size Preference of Women with Chronic Infection: Analysis of Aba Women. *International Journal of Culture and Society* 2(1)60-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11060664>.
- Gribble, J. N. and Bremner, J. (2012b). Achieving a Demographic Dividend. *Population Bulletin*, Vol. 67, No. 2, December, 2012. Population Reference Bureau.
- Kingdom Sunday Mboho, Wisdom Matthew Akpan, Udom Sunday Daniel and Edidiong Anthony Ekoriko (2024). Rural Communities and Cooperative Societies: A Community-Based Alternative for Sustainable Socio-Economic Development in Nigeria, *African Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, ISSN: 2689-5080 Volume 7, Issue 3, 2024 (pp. 57-70). DOI: 10.52589/AJESD-RSHWM3CL.
- Ochinyabo, S. (2021). Rapid Population Growth and Economic Development Issues in Nigeria, *Journal of Economics and Allied Research* vo. 6; Issue 3, Pages 1-13.
- Saviour Sebastian Udo, Udom Sunday Daniel and Clement Etti Willie (2024). Public Administration Policies and Effects on Nigerian Economy. *AKSU Annals of Sustainable Development*, volume 2 Number 1; June 2024. ISSN: (P) 3027-0499; ISSN: (E) 3043-4955. <https://doi.org/10.60787/AASD-v2i1-31>.
- Statistics South Africa (2017). *Wither a Demographic Dividend South Africa: The Overton Window of Political Possibilities*. Pretoria: Statistics South Africa.
- United Nations (2023). *The Sustainable Development Goals Report (2023)*. Special Edition – July 2023, New York, USA: © UNDESA. <https://unstats.un-org/sdgs/report/2023/>.
- United Nations Population Fund (2015). *UNFPA and the Sustainable Development Goals*. <http://www.unfpa.org/resources/unfpa-sustainable-development-goals>.
- USAIDS (2013) Agency Financial Report, FISCAL year 2013.
- USAIDS (2022). *In Danger: UNAIDS Global AIDS Update 2022*.
- World Bank (2015a). *Global Monitoring Report 2015/16: Development of Goals in an Era of Demographic Change*, Washington DC: World Bank.